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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE VESICOVAGINAL
FISTULA REPAIR OUTCOMES IN THE PRESENCE AND
ABSENCE OF OMENTAL PATCH**¹Dr Zaineb Talat, ²Dr Tayyaba Sajid, ³Dr Mehreen Rasheed¹House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

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Abstract:

Background: Vesicovaginal fistula is an exceptionally terrible condition looked by ladies, for the most part, brought about by obstetrical reasons.

Objective: To decide the result of vesicovaginal fistula fix with and without an omental fix.

Patients and Methods: It was a semi exploratory research which was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to September 2018). In which sequential patients gave vesicovaginal fistula were incorporated and randomized into two gatherings. Gathering A was fixed with utilizing omental fix, though, aggregate B was fixed without an omental fix. The information was entered and broke down by utilizing SPSS.

Results: Age conveyance demonstrated that, 2 (9.52%) were in 20-30 years old gathering in gathering A, 1 (4.77%) in Group-B, 8 (38.1%) were in 31-40 years age bunch in Group-An and 10 (47.61%) in Group-B, 7(33.3%) were in 41-50 years age aggregate in Group-An and 8(38.10%) in Group-B while 4 (19%) were in 51-60 years old gathering in Group-An and 2 (9.52%) in Group-B. Term of ailment for VVF fix uncovered that 14 (66.67%) in Group-A and 16 (76.19%) in Group-B have <3 months length while 7(33.33%) in Group-A and 5 (23.81%) in Group-B were having >3 months span. Achievement of the fix was 16 (76.19%) in Group-A and 12 (57.14%) in Group-B.

Conclusion: In our investigation, vesicovaginal fistula fix was more effective with omental fix than without omental fix.

Keywords: Vesico-Vaginal Fistula, Omental Patch, Fistula Repair.

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INTRODUCTION:

Vesicovaginal fistula (VVF) is an anomalous correspondence between the bladder and the vagina which permits the nonstop automatic spilling of pee through the vagina. The presence of VVF as a clinical substance is accepted to have been known to the doctors of people of yore Egypt, with models present in mummies from 2000 BC [1]. Approximately 500,000 new instances of fistula happen because of obstetrical damage all through the world annually [2]. Vesicovaginal fistula (VVF), is generally brought about by drawn-out discouraged work. This undesirable difficulty leaves influenced ladies with consistently spilling pee, abrasion of vulva and vagina, frequently rendering them social outcast [3]. Industrialized countries information demonstrates that reasons for VVF were stomach hysterectomy in 83%, vaginal hysterectomy in 8%, light in 4%, and various in 5%. Indirect logical inconsistency to the study of disease transmission of VVF in the industrialized world, 96.5% were transiently connected with work and delivery [4]. Fistula can be straightforward where tissues are sound and access is great or convoluted, where tissue misfortune is more, get to is weakened or ureteric holes are included. Genuine frequency of VVF isn't Known [5]. previously, the vesicovaginal fistula was believed to be a serious issue yet with cutting edge careful practice, availability of good suture material and anti-infection agents it tends to be restored surgically [6].

Standards of a careful fix of VVF incorporate ideal tissue condition, sufficient vascular supply and opportunity from contamination, aggravation, rot and threat. Alternative of complete extraction of fistulous tract, pressure-free, water-tight, multilayered conclusion with evasion of covering suture line, mediation of solid vascularized tissue between the bladder and vaginal suture lines and persistent postoperative bladder seepage. Transabdominal fix portrayed by O' Connor holds fast to this managing principle [7]. The outcome of vesicovaginal fistula fix is aimed at counteractive action of fix disappointment (repeat) and along these lines improving the physical and psychosocial prosperity of the patient. VVF fix done through stomach course demonstrated variable outcomes with a progress rate of 100% and 63% with and without omental mediation, respectively [8]. Another examination led in Pakistan indicated achievement rate with omental fix intervention was 88% [9].

Different traditionalist or noninvasive medications for vesicovaginal fistulas exist. The most straightforward moderate treatment is bladder

seepage alone. Albeit normally vain, a little detailed arrangement of four patients experienced effective postoperative vesicovaginal fistula conclusion by straightforward bladder drainage [10]. Small fistulas, typically under 3 or 4 mm in width, might be agreeable to basic fulguration, which can be performed at the season of cystoscopy [11]. Fibrin treatment has been utilized to treat rectal fistulas with changing degrees of accomplishment and is presently being connected to treat vesicovaginal fistulas. Case reports have indicated achievement when utilizing this treatment in fistulas that are littler than 3 mm [12]. Other strategies for treatment for vesicovaginal fistula fixes incorporate electrofulguration and laser removal of the fistulous tract [13]. Because most therapeutic treatments have ended up being insufficient, careful adjustment remains the essential strategy for fixing vesicovaginal fistulas. When arranging a fix of these fistulas, the specialist must consider the aetiology, area, and term of the fistula on the grounds that these components will at last direct the planning of fix and the methodology. The planning and approach of vesicovaginal fistula fixes, notwithstanding, remain controversial [14 – 16].

Truly, the methodology picked by the specialist has been managed by the area of the fistula. Methodologies incorporate vaginal, stomach, or consolidated. The stomach approach has customarily been utilized for supratriangular fistulas, though the vaginal methodology has been generally utilized for infratriangular, bladder neck, and proximal urethral fistulas [17]. Transvaginal fixes don't require the extraction of the fistulous tract, consequently discrediting the need to perform ureteral reimplant. For basic, little develop fistulas, a transvaginal methodology, for example, the Latzko system (incomplete colpocleisis), works incredibly well [18]. Combined strategies are regularly held for convoluted fistulas requiring the utilization of omentum or rectus muscle or for vesicovaginal fistulas with a ureteral contribution. Fistulas close or at the ureteral opening may require ureteral reimplantation at the season of VVF fix. This kind of prerequisite would more often than not militate against a totally transvaginal endeavour at a fix. Accomplishment in fixing complex fistulas requires the utilization of a fortifying layer as they have fizzled earlier endeavours at fix, have relentless induration, or are in excess of 2 cm in size, require the utilization of subordinates, for example, a Martius labial fold [19] or a mix peritoneal and labial fold or a fasciocutaneous flap [20]. The target of the present examination was to decide the result of vesicovaginal fistula fix, with and without an omental fix.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

It was a semi exploratory research which was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to September 2018). All the successive VVF patients were incorporated into study and randomized to one of the two fix gatherings. Gathering an, incorporated the patients in which VVF fix was finished with entomb position of an omental fix. Though, in gathering B, no omental fix was utilized for a fix. Result of vesicovaginal fistula fix was estimated regarding fix achievement and disappointment. Patients were marked having vesicovaginal fix disappointment, when there was persevering spillage of pee from vagina following 06 weeks of the medical procedure with a cystoscopic affirmation of the fistula. The prohibition criteria included vesicovaginal fistula because of radiation, danger, intermittent VVF and Vesicovaginal fistula with bladder neck association.

The reasons, strategy, dangers/advantages of the study were disclosed to the patients and composed educated assent was taken. Chosen patients who had given composed educated assent were assigned both of two gatherings, for example, Gathering An and Group B.

The medical procedure was performed by the senior specialists having an affair of over 2 years in a vesicovaginal medical procedure. The patients were separated into two gatherings; Group An incorporated those patients in which vesicovaginal fistula fix was finished with the intervention of omental fix. Gathering B incorporated those patients in which vesicovaginal fistula fix was managed without the mediation of omental fix. General anaesthesia was utilized in every one of these patients. The vesicovaginal fistula was fixed through Trans-stomach course. Guts were opened and rectus muscles were part in the midline chiselling linea alba. The bladder was vertically opened from arch along back divider up to fistula site. Ureteric openings were recognized, 5 Fr bolstering tubes were passed in the two ureters. The bladder was dismembered from vaginal divider up to 1-2 cm below the fistula opening. In gathering A, bladder and vagina was shut independently and omental intervention was made back to the bladder and foremost to the vaginal fix site. In gathering B, the bladder and vagina were shut independently without the intervention of omentum. The ureteric tubes were brought out through bladder

and stomach divider, as ureteric stents. Bladder shut in two layers. Per urethral Foleys catheter was additionally passed. Channel was set in mid-region. Belly was shut and povidone iodine doused bandage was set in the vagina. This dressing was expelled following 24 hours. Postoperatively, patients were surveyed about the spilling of pee from vagina preceding release by checking the soakage of sterile cushions and on resulting subsequent meet-ups. Ultimate result was surveyed toward the finish of 06 weeks after expulsion of Foley's catheter.

Information of the patient, who satisfied the consideration criteria, was gathered through a pre-planned survey; information was gathered, coded and dissected on SPSS. Recurrence and rates were determined and tables were shaped for factors, for example, age dispersion, the reason for fistula and result of VVF fix. Mean + standard deviation for the time of patient and length of infection was determined. Chi-square test was utilized to think about the VVF fix result in the two gatherings. P-Value of <0.05 was taken as huge. Stratification was done as far as age, aetiology of VVF.

RESULTS:

In this investigation, a sum of 42 patients was selected in the wake of satisfying the incorporation/avoidance criteria to decide the result of vesicovaginal fistula fix with and without omental fix mediation.

Age appropriation of the patients is appeared Table I, where 2(9.52%) were in 20-30 years old gathering in gathering A, 1(4.77%) in Group-B, 8(38.1%) were in 31-40 years age bunch in Group-An and 10(47.61%) in Group-B, 7(33.3%) were in 41-50 years age assemble in Group-An and 8(38.10%) in Group-B while 4(19%) were in 51-60 years old gathering in Group-An and 2(9.52%) in Group-B. Term of ailment for VVF fix uncovered that 14(66.67%) in Group-A and 16(76.19%) in Group-B, have <3 months span while 7(33.33%) in Group-A and 5(23.81%) in Group-B were having >3 months length.

The accomplishment of the fix was 16(76.19%) in Group-A and 12(57.14%) in Group-B while 5(23.81%) in Group-A and 9(42.86%) in Group-B were recorded as fizzled, with a p estimation of 0.03, for contrast.

Table – I: Stratification for the success of VVF repair for patients

Age (years)	Group A No of patients (% age)	Group B No of patients (% age)
20-30	02(9.52%)	01(4.77%)
31-40	08(38.10%)	10(47.6%)
41-50	07(33.33%)	08(38.1%)
51-60	04(19.05%)	02(9.5%)
Duration		
<3 months	14(66.67%)	16(76.1%)
>3 months	07(33.33%)	05(23.8%)
Duration of illness (mean $\pm$ SD in days)		
	56.21 $\pm$ 11.16 days	51.176 $\pm$ 9.32 days
Outcome		
Success	16(76.19%)	12(57%)
Failure	05(23.81%)	09(42.8%)

Table – II: Characteristics of patients (N=42)

Age (years)	Group A		Group B	
	No. of patients	Success No. (%age)	No. of patients	Success No. (%age)
20-30	2	2(100)	01	1(100)
31-40	8	7(87.7)	10	6(60)
41-50	7	5(71.43)	08	4(50)
51-60	4	2(50)	02	1(50)
Aetiology				
Surgical	11	9(81.82)	13	7(53.85)
Obstetrical	10	7(70)	08	5(62.5)
Duration of disease				
<3 months	14	12(85.7)	16	10(62.5)
>3 months	07	4(57)	05	2(40)

Stratification for the accomplishment of VVF fix for the age of the patients demonstrated that 2(100%) out of 2 patients in Group An and 1(100%) out of 1 in Group-B, between 20-30 years old while having a fruitful fix. 7(87.5%) out of 8 in Group-An and 6 (60%) out of 10 in Group-B, between 31-40 years, 5 (71.43%) out of 7 in Group-An and 4 (half) out of 8 in Group-B between 41-50 years while 2(50%) out of 4 in Group-An and 1(50%) out of 2 in Group-B,

between 51-60 years old, were having effective fix.

Stratification for accomplishment of VVF fix for etiology of the malady demonstrated that 9 (81.82%) out of 11 patients in Group-An and 7 (53.85%) out of 13 in Group B with careful etiology were having fruitful fix while, 7 (70%) out of 10 in Group An and 5 (62.5%) out of 8 in Group B with obstetrical aetiology, were having effective fix.

Stratification for achievement of VVF fix for length of sickness demonstrated that 12 (85.71%) out of 14 patients in Group A and 10 (62.5%) out of 16 in Group B with <3 long periods of term were having effective fix while, 4 (57.14%) out of 7 in Group A and 2 (40%) out of 5 in Group B with >3 long periods of span of malady, have fruitful fix.

DISCUSSION:

The predominance of the horribleness changes from nation to nation and mainland to landmass because of the fundamental causative elements. As indicated by the World Health Organization (WHO) estimation, in creating nations every year five million ladies endure serious maternal bleakness, obstetric fistulae being on the highest priority on the rundown. It is additionally evaluated that at present in excess of 2 million ladies are hanging tight for medical procedure worldwide and around 50 to 100,000 new cases are included every year for the most part in Africa and Asia. In created nations despite what might be expected, fistula is identified with Gynecologic surgery [21].

We directed this investigation, considering the error of aftereffects of VVF fix with omental intervention, henceforth needs additional proof and not many examinations have been distributed. The trans-abdominal approach was received because of the reason that the greater part of the cases had complex or supratriangular fistulae and in our setup, we utilized this methodology for the most part because of solid trust that VVF ought to ideally be close with numerous layers without strain and utilizing tissue intervention so the more prominent momentum is normally utilized when the stomach approach is picked. We recorded 76.19% achievement rate in omental fix amass when contrasted with 57.14% in without omental fix, our outcomes are tantamount with the consequences of Evans and colleagues, [22] recording more accomplishment with omental fix when contrasted with without omental fix, yet the achievement rate of their examination was 100% versus 63%, the distinction in lower achievement rate might be because of the reason that we had just 2 years of experience in regards to fix of fistula which may not be particularly adequate, however the higher achievement rate demonstrates that fix with omental fix is superior to without.

Our outcomes are in concurrence with an examination led by Uprety D and collaborators, [23] who recorded 56% of achievement rate in VVF fixed without an omental fix. Aftereffects of Nawaz H and specialists, [8] demonstrated achievement rate of 87.93% for a fix of VVF with an omental fix.

Another examination by Tariq M and associates, [24] who assessed the result of vesicovaginal fistula fix with and without mediation of omental fix, uncovered 96% achievement rate as contrast with 84%, these discoveries is likewise in concurrence with the consequence of the present investigation in regards to more accomplishment in Group-A patients who were treated with omental fix.

Langkilde NC, in an examination, [25] to discover the result of vesicovaginal fistula conclusion strategies over a 10-year time span, 23 had a stomach fix and 7, have a vaginal fix of the 30 patients with postoperative fistulae. A triumph rate of 90% was accomplished after a first conclusion strategy; the consequences of this examination are likewise in concurrence with the present investigation. Stratification for age, length of sickness, and sort of aetiology of vesicovaginal fistula likewise uncovered practically break even with achievement in the two gatherings.

CONCLUSION:

The consequences of the examination demonstrated that result of vesicovaginal fistula fix with the omental fix is better than vesicovaginal fistula fix without an omental fix and can be utilized in our standard practice, which might be additionally expanded with the expansion in experience.

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